

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	APARRU8C
Principle Investigator	Johan Larsson
Structure/Description	<p>Hexadecyl-beta-maltoside-<i>d</i>₃₁</p>
Code	AEL02127
Producer	Anna Leung
Mass	520 mg
% Deuteration	98% (±2%)
Analyses	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of hexadecyl-beta-maltoside- d_{31} (AEL02127) in CD_3OD (400 MHz).

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of hexadecyl-beta-maltoside- d_{31} (AEL02127) in CD_3OD (400 MHz) (expansion).

Figure 3. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of hexadecyl-beta-maltoside- d_{31} (AEL02127) in CD_3OD (100 MHz).

Figure 4. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of hexadecyl-beta-maltoside- d_{31} (AEL02127) in CD_3OD (100 MHz) (expansion).

Figure 5. ESI-MS(+) of hexadecyl-beta-maltoside- d_{31} (AEL02127): m/z calculated for $C_{28}H_{23}D_{31}NaO_{11}$ $[M+Na]^+$ as 620.9; found: 620.5.

Calculation of % Deuteration from MS Isotope Distribution									
Note: Always label the lowest m/z peak as Peak No. 1 & increment each subsequent peak by 1 m/z unit									
Parent Ion Peak No.	Theoretical % D for Peak	Peak Area	Corrected Peak Area	Contribution of Peak to Overall % D	¹³ C Isotopic Distribution from ChemDraw:		Theoretical % D for Peak	Corrected Peak Area	Amount (%) of compound at Theoretical % D
1	93,5	7,9000E+00	7,9000E+00	8,1	¹³ C # 2	30,3	93,5	7,9000E+00	8,6
2	96,8	2,9200E+01	2,6806E+01	28,3	¹³ C # 3	2,7	96,8	2,6806E+01	29,2
3	100,0	6,6100E+01	5,7039E+01	62,2			100,0	5,7039E+01	62,2
4			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
5			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
6			0,0000E+00	0,0	Total Corrected Area of all isotopic Peaks		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
7			0,0000E+00	0,0	9,1745E+01		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
8			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
9			0,0000E+00	0,0	Average % Deuteration of Molecule		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
10			0,0000E+00	0,0	98,5		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
11			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
12			0,0000E+00	0,0	Error = +/- 2 %		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
13			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
14			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
15			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
16			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
17			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
18			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
19			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
20			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
21			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
22			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
23			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
24			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
25			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
26			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
27			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
28			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
29			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
30			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0

Figure 6. Calculation of deuteration percentage of the -C₁₅D₃₁ portion of the alkyl group of hexadecyl-beta-maltoside-d₃₁ (AEL02127) based on ESI-MS.